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EC2U Think Tank 2

Circular Economy – Key to Sustainability and Change

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I. Summary Report

A. EC2U Think Tanks

As a catalyst for ideas the Think Tanks enable the circulation of knowledge and solutions. They are designed to open an exchange between citizens, scientists, and policy makers to discuss pressing societal issues. The EC2U Think Tanks are a way of learning from each other on a local and European level. They help to come up with ways of getting involved, of participating, and enabling change faster.

The Think Tanks are a central measure within the pillar of European Engagement, one of three focus areas of EC2U WP 7 “Science with and for society”. Looking at the world we live in, there has never been a more important time to come together and listen to diverse perspectives and work with different types of stakeholders to co-create shared visions and new solutions. The EC2U Think Tanks assemble stakeholders and change agents from as many perspectives as possible - citizens, public authorities, scientists, school teachers, journalists, politicians, students etc.

B. Think Tank Charter

One of the goals of the EC2U Alliance is to foster dialogue within our communities and within Europe, to reach out and bring different stakeholders together to discuss the central issues of our time. The Work Package 7 Board decided that the EC2U Think Tanks should explicitly commit to a certain value set. We therefore formulated and approved a Think Tank Charta that ensures that the EC2U Think Tanks are a safe place of respectful exchange and constructive discussion¹. All participants and organizers of an EC2U Think Tank had to acknowledge and support this bedrock of the Think Tank for the good of everyone involved. Important passages are, amongst others:

“As a participant in the THINK TANK, I commit to:

*Respect our European values, as set in Art. 2 of the Treaty on the European Union:
human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human
rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities, which is part of what it*

¹ The Think Tank Charta is partly taken from the [Charta of the Conference on the Future of Europe](#) in the spirit of which the Think Tank has taken place.

means to be European and to engage respectfully with each other. These values are common to all EU Member States and implicitly EC2U members in a society in which pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men must prevail.”

[...]

“As a party organizing a THINK TANK, I commit to:

Allow everyone to express their voice freely and equally consider all expressed views.

Promote events that are inclusive and accessible for all citizens, including by publishing the details of the event in English and the local language on a digital platform.

Encourage diversity in the debates, by actively supporting the participation of citizens from all walks of life, irrespective of gender, sexual orientation, age, socioeconomic background, religion and/or level of education.”

(see Annex 1 for Complete Think Tank Charta)

C. 2nd EC2U Think Tank: Circular Economy – Key to Sustainability and Change

The topic of the Think Tank was “Circular economy – Key to Sustainability and Change” was chosen by the Work Package 7 Board and EC2U Executive Committee by vote. The purpose of the second Think Tank on Circular Economy was:

- to extend the local and European network,
- to identify local problems and solutions in building up a circular economy,
- to take a step towards sustainability in the long run.

Accordingly, the second EC2U Think Tank consisted of seven local Think Tanks (held in the native languages of the EC2U community), a joint presentation at the EC2U Forum in Pavia, and a policy recommendation.

The synthesized outcomes of the local Think Tanks were summarized and presented to stimulate public debate and identify good ideas that can be acted upon.

Circular economy consists of three principles: 1. Eliminate waste and pollution, 2. Circulate products and materials (keep products and material in use as much as possible), 3. Regenerate nature. “We must transform every element of our take-make-waste system: how we manage resources, how we make and use products, and what we do with the materials afterwards. Only then can we create a thriving circular economy that can benefit everyone within the limits of our planet. [...] The circular economy gives us the tools to tackle climate change and biodiversity loss together, while addressing important social needs” (ellenmacarthurfoundation.org). Circular economy is not an end in itself but a means to an end: better environmental quality, economic growth, and social well-being.

Circular economy and Sustainability have many things in common, as well as controversial or debatable issues. We were interested in the ways in which circular economy can increase sustainability. Sustainability refers to a development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987). “Sustainability can be defined as a situation in which human activity is conducted to conserve the functions of the earth’s ecosystems, or a transformation of human lifestyle that increases the likelihood that living conditions will continuously support security, well-being, and health, particularly by maintaining the supply of non-replaceable goods and services, or an indefinite perpetuation of all life forms”. (Geissdoerfer et al, 2017)

1. Proceedings

From January to March 2022, every Partner of the EC2U Alliance held a 2 to 2,5 hour-long Think Tank – to comply with local Covid-19 regulations either as an online meeting or on-site.

Coimbra	Iași	Jena	Pavia	Poitiers	Salamanca	Turku
24.03.22	16.02.22	17.01.22	28.02.22	03.03.22	23.02.22	15.02.22
Online	Online	Online	Online	On site	On site	Online

In total 90 people participated in the local Think Tanks. Invited stakeholders included:

- from the university: researchers, students, green/sustainable development offices,

- municipalities,
- businesses,
- associations engaged in the topic of circular economy/sustainability.

(see Annex 2 for complete list of participants)

Figure 1 : Screenshots and photographs from the EC2U Think Tank 2022

All Think Tanks followed a common script that was jointly developed by the Work Package 7 Board and send out to all participants before the event (see Annex 3). Each Board Member also functioned as the moderator or recorder of the local Think Tank.

Figure 2: Example of Communicating a local Think Tank (here: Jena).

Figure 3: News coverage of the Salamanca Think Tank

2. Questions

At the core of the Think Tank were five questions:

- **Question 1 - Motivation:** What motivated/motivates the stakeholders to become engaged in circular economy?
 - Collect the motivations of the stakeholders.
 - Identify the main areas in which the stakeholder has experiences and/or areas considered as being very important at the local level (e.g. companies can have specific areas – like waste, for a local garbage collecting company, or pollution

etc., while NGOs, administration and policy people may have several areas of interest.).

- **Question 2 - Problems:** What are the specific problems and challenges that the stakeholders have attempted to solve?
 - Collect the initial problems and challenges.
- **Question 3 - Solutions:** Which solutions did the stakeholders come up with and implement? What helped them along the way? What hindered them along the way?
 - Collect solutions.
- **Question 4 – Remaining Challenges:** What are the next challenges that the stakeholders want to tackle/Or: What are problems that they yet have to solve?
 - Collect unsolved problems
- **Question 5 – EC2U Brainstorming:** Brainstorm ways in which the EC2U Alliance can become a more sustainable endeavor.

3. Evaluation

For the evaluation of the Think Tank a central feedback survey was provided. Each member of the Work Package 7 Board who acted as moderator or facilitator of the Think Tank was free to translate the English template into the native language. Questions included:

- How satisfied are you with the Think Tank? (*1 not satisfied – 5 highly satisfied*)
- Open Feedback: What could be improved? (*Open Text Box*)
- Other Comments (*Open Text Box*)

The overall satisfaction rate with the Think Tank was 4,5 out 5. Open feedback included:

Very positive to have had the opportunity to share visions and experiences with different stakeholders (industry, students, researchers, civil organizations, farming and agriculture...); usually there is rarely the opportunity to listen to so different and even contradictory visions

More time for discussion

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Continuation of the dialogue after the Think Tank

Interesting to meet people from other local institutions who are engaged in the same field

Social media platforms or other channels to share good practices and useful materials

Not all local stakeholders in the field of circular economy knew each other before the Think Tank. Thus, it proved useful to have local Think Tanks as a first step to establish and enhance local networks that then can act as strong partners on a European level. During the Pavia Forum in April 2022, this European level became visible with the joint presentation of all results.

II. Key Findings of Think Tanks

A. Key Findings with regard to stakeholders

1. Overview University

University	Motivation	Problems	Solutions	Remaining Challenges
Turku	To proactively foster well-being and a sustainable future through the University's missions (education, research, third mission) and everyday activities	Requires communicating and implementing new ways of thinking and doing which takes time.	Sustainable Campus Action Plan in the making to promote to the university community everyday actions following the principles of sustainability	Raising awareness
Poitiers	Steering the process and meeting students' expectations	Environmental actions are sometimes in contradiction with general public contracting rules	Introduce sustainability and social responsibility criteria in contracts	Generalize sustainable development and social responsibility criteria in procurement
Jena	Work together and get others involved for change; Research: define the concept	Technological solutions easier than systemic solutions	Implement an institutional structure and attribute a fixed budget for sustainability issues.	High consumption of heat and energy in university facilities. Address social sustainability

Pavia	<p>Reduce the use of private vehicles and related CO2 emissions.</p> <p>Reduce waste and increase students' awareness about environmental issues</p>	<p>Getting the civil society and local stakeholders involved, lack of local actors' proactive behaviors</p>	<p>Increase the communication and the engagement activities</p>	<p>Coordination and cooperation with other local stakeholders</p>
Coimbra	<p>Contribute to a sustainable future and to the adoption of life models that consider and respect the human dimension, with sustainability practices to be consciously implemented in the management of the entity itself, to be transmitted through teaching and to be developed by</p>	<p>The intense daily activity of universities generates environmental impacts, with overuse of resources and exorbitant production of waste, resulting from the consumption of resources in UC spaces, the travels made and the behavior of each and every one who works,</p>	<p>Political commitment and a Strategic Plan with a pillar "environment and climate action", with a clear vision + a dedicated office + very active student associations</p>	<p>Energy inefficiency of historic buildings; traffic in the historic area; specific waste streams needing integrated management procedures; promote the use of goods with reused materials & legal barriers; raise general awareness of an academic community of</p>

	research (new solutions and new paths to circularity)	studies or simply visits it		almost 30,000 people; improve circularity indicators and own ecological footprint measurement model
Iasi	intrinsic (individual and organizational level) and extrinsic: personal values (desire to change things for the better), organizational values (environmental and social responsibility) and financial opportunities (call for projects available)	Lack of trust in own power to move things in a good direction; Lack of circular economy in formal education	Networking and common projects	Increase intersectorial collaboration; Increase funds for research in the field
Salamanca	Contribute to sustainable development, from research, training and knowledge	Structural inertia and bureaucracy; lack of coordination, Very limited budgets	Achievable objectives at the university and municipal levels; Facilitate participatory forums and	Promote multidisciplinary teams; Reduce the carbon footprint + energy

	transfer to society		communication channels	expenditure in institutions
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Common issues: problems linked to ineffective coordination as well lack of budget, of effective information and communication; how to enable sustainable procurement; how to engage stakeholders within and outside the university.

2. Overview Cities

	Motivation	Problems	Solutions	Remaining Challenges
Turku	Strive towards sustainable city development to create positive impacts on well-being, economy (new businesses) and environment	Costs and rush stall decision-making. Multi-stakeholder collaboration requires better understanding of different actors' roles and smart decision-making	Make investment and procurement decisions aligned with CE; process and share information for different stakeholders.	Take steps from plans to concrete implementation. Focus next on transportation and mobility
Poitiers	Work with all the actors of the territory on the themes of short cycles and recovery	Supporting change in habits and behavior	Conducting a psychological study with the help of a PhD student	Pursue and implement actions to promote behavioral change
Jena	Creation of a livable and	Communicate and implement change within the current	Strategically implement circular concepts in city policy, in	Adapt existing buildings and their surroundings to

	environmentally friendly city	political and legal frameworks. Personnel and financial shortage	city events or daycare centers. Enabling circulation among citizens	climate change, Develop infrastructure for sustainable mobility
Pavia	Reduce urban waste (food, appliances, cigarettes). Spread the idea of sustainable mobility	Enhance the collaboration with public and private actors and promote a non-consumerist logic based on re-conceptualizing the idea of waste	Spread the culture of sustainability, create synergies among actors, engage citizens through workshops/city tours	More commitment is needed from public authorities, legislative frameworks need to be updated with respect to circular practices (e.g. concept of waste)
Coimbra	Awareness of all the community in the practices of circularity; conservation of resources based on the natural heritage; reduce the city production of emissions and	Indifference generated by inaction and lack of political prioritization of cities to CE; cultural issues: consumer behavior or the lack of knowledge about the CE	First step: developing a “Roadmap for the Circular Economy”	Removal of issues of circularity of the economy from the priorities of the political agenda

	waste; decelerate/ minimize the effects of climate change	concept and its implications		
Iasi	Similar for all three categories of stakeholders - intrinsic (individual and organizational level) and extrinsic: personal values (desire to change things for the better), organizational values (environmental and social responsibility) and financial opportunities (call for projects available)	Reduced citizen involvement, Reluctant entrepreneurs	Training and technical assistance Iasi participant in “Zero Waste Municipalities”	Reduce the risk of “greenwashing”, Increase waste management infrastructures, mainly in rural areas
Salamanca	Contribute to sustainable development from research, training and knowledge	Structural inertia and bureaucracy; lack of coordination,	Achievable objectives at the university and municipal levels; Facilitate participatory	Promote multidisciplinary teams; Reduce the carbon footprint + energy

	transfer to society	very limited budgets	forums and communication channels	expenditure in institutions
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Common issues: developing a roadmap to more urban sustainability and/or achieving carbon-neutrality, raising city-wide awareness, dealing with current, often hindering legal framework, lack of budget, need to improve the collaboration and engagement of public entities.

3. Overview Businesses

	Motivation	Problems	Solutions	Remaining Challenges
Turku	To be an influencer in the industrial policy and support circular economy in different parts of the value chain	Lack of investment funds. Broad systemic thinking is needed instead of optimizing only selected parts of the system.	Measuring footprints and creating ecosystems (actors, knowledge, research) around different material streams.	Issuing stronger enforcement measures e.g. via VAT exemption and obligation to recycle and instructions to procuring units from suppliers.
Poitiers	Being a committed, ecologically-minded entrepreneur	Work with French products that have real traceability and respect the types of protocols already in place	Working with natural + minimally-processed materials using a process that respects the environment +	Moving from laboratory experimentation as part of a start-up to production on an industrial scale

			the charter of labels	
Jena	Create a better world for future generations. Implement new sustainability regulations	Sensitize entrepreneurs to Circular Economy, staff and financial shortage	Implement sustainable guidelines for procurement	Raise awareness and prevent waste in the first place
Pavia	Transform “waste” into resources, develop alternative, ethical and socially responsible ways of producing	Create industrial symbiosis, communicate the value proposition to prospect clients, scaling-up	Find partnering firms, diversify the product portfolio, innovate	Scaling up, communicate the value proposition, encourage producers to shift to the circular economy paradigm
Coimbra	Need to awaken and support business to the urgency of developing and implementing new materials, technologies and business models that allow greater resource efficiency and a	Need to increase the use of materials from renewable sources, to reduce of waste production throughout the life cycle of products, to upcycle, to improve energy efficiency, to increase	Dematerializati on and materials engineering, search for more efficient materials / technologies / solutions, focus on safe and sustainable design, eco-design; life cycle analysis;	Prioritize the use of renewable raw materials from the agroforestry sector and boost the flow of national industrial materials to develop new products, with a focus on energy efficiency,

	more sustainable development of our economy	durability and extension of lifetime of products and to apply systems sensing + de-materialization	increasing the sustainability of non-circular solutions	sustainability and circularity, business still very focused on the costs of transitioning to circular solutions and with difficult access to financing
Iasi	Similar for all three category of stakeholders - intrinsic (individual and organizational level) and extrinsic: personal values (desire to change things for the better), organizational values (environmental and social responsibility) and financial opportunities (call for projects available)	Lack of traceability + verifiable indicators, Deficient secondary legislation (for applying rules), State institutions prefer classic paper	Personal initiatives and involvement, Clusters of creative industries, social enterprises	Develop the market for recycled materials; increase all stakeholders' awareness

Salamanca	<p>New lines of work, promote public/private lines of research, financial support</p>	<p>Difficulty in obtaining appliances to prepare for reuse, new lines of research (clothes, mattresses, ...)</p>	<p>Provide appliances, materials to prepare them for reuse and / or recycling of parts. Effective financial support</p>	<p>Promote circular economy (subsidy, incentive)</p> <p>Compliance with current legislation traceability of materials</p>
	<p>Take advantage of our natural resources and especially organic by-products of the agri-food sector; solution for rural depopulation</p>	<p>Reduce production costs; coordination among administration, industry, scientific community + consumers</p>	<p>Invest in R + D + I; encourage symbiosis strategies among industries (waste from one industry can be the raw material of another); New degrees and masters</p>	

Common issues: lack of proper funding and investment in circular business models, lack of networks/clusters of like-minded businesses, communicate the value proposition to clients, scaling up, develop economies of scale, implement sustainable supply chains, promote changes in the current legislation.

B. Key Findings with regard to location

1. Findings Think Tank - Turku

Turku University

Motivation: To proactively foster well-being and a sustainable future through the University's missions (education, research, third mission) and everyday activities.

Problems: Requires communicating and implementing new ways of thinking and doing which take time.

Solutions: Sustainable Campus Action Plan in the making to promote to the university community everyday actions following the principles of sustainability.

Remaining Challenges: Raising awareness.

Good Practices: Sustainable Campus Life Working Group, Carbon neutrality by 2025.

Turku City

Motivation: Strive towards sustainable city development to create positive impacts on well-being, economy (new businesses), and environment.

Problems: Costs and rush stall decision-making. Multi-stakeholder collaboration requires better understanding of different actors' roles and smart decision-making.

Solutions: Make investment and procurement decisions aligned with CE; process and share information for different stakeholders.

Remaining Challenges: Take steps from plans to concrete implementation. Focus next on transportation and mobility.

Good Practices: Circular Turku Roadmap.

Figure 4: Circular Turku Roadmap

Turku Businesses

Motivation: To be an influencer in industrial policy and support circular economy in different parts of the value chain.

Problems: Lack of investment funds. Broad systemic thinking is needed instead of optimizing only selected parts of the system.

Solutions: Measuring footprints and creating ecosystems (actors, knowledge, research) around different material streams.

Remaining Challenges: Issuing stronger enforcement measures e.g. via VAT exemption and obligation to recycle and instructions to procuring units from suppliers.

Good Practices: Circular Economy Visitor Centre brings circular economy to life, by, first, functioning as a learning environment for citizens and school children; second, being a showroom for regional companies and other operators in the region; and third, acting as a builder of cooperation networks.

Figure 5: Circular Economy Visitor Centre Turku

2. Findings Think Tank - Poitiers

Poitiers University

Motivation: Steering the process and meeting students' expectations.

Problems: Environmental actions are sometimes in contradiction with general public contracting rules.

Solutions: Introduce sustainability and social responsibility criteria in contracts.

Remaining Challenges: Generalize sustainable development and social responsibility criteria in procurement.

Good Practices: Obtained the DDRS label to implement its commitment to the ecological and energy transition.

Figure 6: DDRS Label

Poitiers City

Motivation: Work with all the actors of the territory on the themes of short cycles and recovery.

Problems: Supporting change in habits and behavior.

Solutions: Conducting a psychological study with the help of a PhD student.

Remaining Challenges: Pursue and implement actions to promote behavioural change.

Good Practices: Setting up collective composting sites.

Figure 7: Composting Sites in Poitiers

Poitiers Businesses

Motivation: Being a committed, ecologically-minded entrepreneur.

Problems: Work with French products that have real traceability and respect the types of protocols already in place.

Solutions: Working with natural, minimally processed materials using a process that respects the environment, the charter of labels.

Remaining Challenges: Moving from laboratory experimentation as part of a start-up to production on an industrial scale

Good Practices: A process for deconstructing biosourced and renewable plant material (dry with metal balls and therefore without solvents or water) to extract molecules with specific properties.

Figure 8: New processes for more circularity (<https://biosedev.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/4.jpg>)

3. Findings Think Tank - Jena

Jena University

Motivation: Work together and get others involved for change; Research: define the concept.

Problems: Technological solutions easier than systemic solutions.

Solutions: Implement an institutional structure and attribute a fixed budget for sustainability issues.

Remaining Challenges: High consumption of heat and energy in university facilities. Address social sustainability.

Good Practices: Green Office, Sustainability Working Group with the Senate, Pallet furniture for the Campus.

Jena City

Motivation: Creation of a livable and environmentally friendly city.

Problems: Communicate and implement change within the current political and legal frameworks. Personnel and financial shortage.

Solutions: Strategically implement circular concepts in city policy, in city events or daycare centers. Enabling circulation among citizens.

Remaining Challenges: Adapt existing buildings and their surroundings to climate change, Develop infrastructure for sustainable mobility.

Good Practices: Repair cafés, Food-sharing projects, Give away shelves, Fairy tale booklet for schools, Fair shopping guide.

Figure 9: Teaching Circularity to kids with engaging materials (<https://zebraluchs.de/moehrchenheft>)

Jena Businesses

Motivation: Create a better world for future generations. Implement new sustainability regulations.

Problems: Sensitize entrepreneurs to Circular Economy, staff and financial shortage.

Solutions: Implement sustainable guidelines for procurement.

Remaining Challenges: Raise awareness and prevent waste in the first place.

Good Practices: Refill Jena, Promotion of regional products.

4. Findings Think Tank - Pavia

Pavia University

Motivation: Reduce the use of private vehicles and related CO₂ emissions. Reduce waste and increase students' awareness about environmental issues.

Problems: Getting the civil society and local stakeholders involved, lack of local actors' proactive behaviors.

Solutions: Increase the communication and the engagement activities.

Remaining Challenges: Coordination and cooperation with other local stakeholders.

Good Practices: Establishment of OSA - Office for Sustainable Actions; Bike sharing to move in town; Installation of water dispensers in several university sites; Increase students' awareness (colleges).

Pavia City

Motivation: Reduce urban waste (food, appliances, cigarettes). Spread the idea of sustainable mobility.

Problems: Enhance the collaboration with public and private actors and promote a non-consumerist logic based on re-conceptualizing the idea of waste.

Solutions: Spread the culture of sustainability for instance through art exhibitions (e.g., Lady Be and Global Warming), create synergies among local actors, engage citizens through workshops/city tours.

Remaining Challenges: More commitment is needed from public authorities; legislative frameworks need to be updated with respect to circular practices (e.g. concept of waste).

Good Practices: Repair Café, FIAB: promoting sustainable mobility, Spreading among citizens the circular practices (e.g., events Plasticfree)

Pavia Businesses

Motivation: Transform "waste" into resources, develop alternative, ethical and socially responsible ways of producing.

Problems: Create industrial symbiosis, communicate the value proposition to prospect clients, scaling-up.

Solutions: Find partnering firms, diversify the product portfolio, innovate.

Remaining Challenges: Scaling up, communicate the value proposition, encourage producers to shift to the circular economy paradigm.

Good Practices: Transform what is commonly defined as « waste » into a resource, Reduce the food waste, propose sustainable alternatives to fast fashion.

5. Findings Think Tank - Coimbra

Coimbra University

Motivation: Contribute to a sustainable future and to the adoption of life models that consider and respect the human dimension, with sustainability practices to be consciously implemented in the management of the entity itself, to be transmitted through teaching and to be developed by research (new solutions and new paths to circularity).

Problems: The intense daily activity of universities generates environmental impacts, with overuse of resources and exorbitant production of waste, resulting from the consumption of resources in UC spaces, the travels made and the behavior of each and every one who works, studies or simply visits it.

Solutions: Political commitment and a Strategic Plan with a pillar “environment and climate action”, with a clear vision + a dedicated office + very active student associations.

Remaining Challenges: Energy inefficiency of historic buildings; traffic in the historic area; specific waste streams needing integrated management procedures; promote the use of goods with reused materials & legal barriers; raise general awareness of an academic community of almost 30,000 people; improve circularity indicators and own ecological footprint measurement model.

Good Practices: Political determination and involvement: Strategic Plan with a pillar “Environment and climate action”, Sustainable Development Office, Sustainable Development Observatory, [Dedicated webpage](#)

Sustainability Guide to Students, Energy for Sustainability Initiative, Climate clock (the first climate clock in Portugal was inaugurated at the Academic Association of Coimbra - AAC), Green Community (implementation of initiatives to make events more sustainable – e.g.: reducing the use of environmentally unfriendly materials)

Figure 10: Strategic Sustainability Plan

Figure 11: Climate Clock

Coimbra City

Motivation: Awareness of all the community in the practices of circularity; conservation of resources based on the natural heritage; reduce the city production of emissions and waste; decelerate/minimize the effects of climate change.

Problems: Indifference generated by inaction and lack of political prioritization of cities to CE; cultural issues: consumer behavior or the lack of knowledge about the CE concept and its implications.

Solutions: First step: developing a “Roadmap for the Circular Economy”

Remaining Challenges: Removal of issues of circularity of the economy from the priorities of the political agenda

Good Practices: Roadmap for the Circular Economy (in development by Municipality), Centro Green Deal (circular public purchases with CE principles), Regional Institutional Pact for Circular Economy

Figure 12: Roadmap for a Circular City

Coimbra Businesses

Motivation: Need to awaken and support business to the urgency of developing and implementing new materials, technologies and business models that allow greater resource efficiency and a more sustainable development of our economy.

Problems: Need to increase the use of materials from renewable sources, to reduce of waste production throughout the life cycle of products, to upcycle, to improve energy efficiency, to increase durability and extension of life time of products and to apply systems sensing and dematerialization.

Solutions: Dematerialization and materials engineering, search for more efficient materials/ technologies/solutions, focus on safe and sustainable design, eco-design; life cycle analysis; increasing the sustainability of non-circular solutions.

Remaining Challenges: Prioritize the use of renewable raw materials from the agroforestry sector and boost the flow of national industrial materials to develop new products, with a focus on energy efficiency, sustainability and circularity; business still very focused on the costs of transitioning to circular solutions and with difficult access to financing.

Good Practices: “Hands On” workshops to help developing business circular strategies, Services to support the development of business models that are as “circular” as possible, E-Waste (waste of electrical and electronic equipment).

6. Findings Think Tank - Iasi

Iasi University

Motivation: Similar for all three categories of stakeholders - intrinsic (individual and organizational level) and extrinsic: personal values (desire to change things for the better), organizational values (environmental and social responsibility) and financial opportunities (call for projects available).

Problems: Lack of trust in own power to move things in a good direction; Lack of circular economy in formal education.

Solutions: Networking and common projects.

Remaining Challenges: Increase intersectorial collaboration; Increase funds for research in the field.

Iasi City

Motivation: Similar for all three category of stakeholders - intrinsic (individual and organizational level) and extrinsic: personal values (desire to change things for the better), organizational values (environmental and social responsibility) and financial opportunities (call for projects available).

Problems: Reduced citizen involvement, Reluctant entrepreneurs.

Solutions: Training and technical assistance Iasi participant in “Zero Waste Municipalities”.

Remaining Challenges: Reduce the risk of “greenwashing”, Increase waste management infrastructures, mainly in rural areas.

Good Practices: *The Urban Center for Good Initiatives – CUIB:* multidimensional space (bistro, local products store, space for cultural and educational events). Aims to support local producers and community, diminish negative impact on environment.

REDU - Reused, Recycled and Upcycled Clothes and Accessories” (Green Group): Integrated and total waste management solutions for 6 main waste streams associated with households and SMEs (WEEE, plastics, PET, glass, lighting bulbs, cardboard).

ECOTIC Caravan: educational project aiming to raise awareness on environmental protection and sustainable development, focusing on household, electrical and electronic waste (HEEW). Designed for both general public and children aged 6-14 years. Mobile exhibition with disassembled HEEW, to increase awareness towards risks of poor electric-waste management.

Iasi Businesses

Motivation: Similar for all three categories of stakeholders - intrinsic (individual and organizational level) and extrinsic: personal values (desire to change things for the better), organizational values (environmental and social responsibility) and financial opportunities (call for projects available).

Problems: Lack of traceability + verifiable indicators, Deficient secondary legislation (for applying rules), State institutions prefer classic paper.

Solutions: Personal initiatives and involvement, Clusters of creative industries, Social enterprises.

Remaining Challenges: Develop the market for recycled materials; increase all stakeholders' awareness.

7. Findings Think Tank - Salamanca

Salamanca City/University

Motivation: Contribute to sustainable development, from research, training and knowledge transfer to society.

Problems: Structural inertia and bureaucracy; Lack of coordination; Very limited budgets.

Solutions: Achievable objectives at the university and municipal levels; Facilitate participatory forums and communication channels.

Remaining Challenges: Promote multidisciplinary teams; Reduce the carbon footprint + energy expenditure in institutions.

Salamanca Agriculture/farming

Motivation: Take advantage of our natural resources and the especially organic by-products of the agri-food sector; solution for rural depopulation.

Problems: reduce production costs; coordination among administration, industry, scientific community + consumers.

Solutions + Remaining Challenges: invest in R + D + I; encourage symbiosis strategies among industries (waste from one industry can be the raw material of another); New degrees and masters.

Good Practices: *Poctep Reinova_S.i.*: pilot experiences with companies that used their kale waste to make other products such as cookies or snacks, waste from making jams to make jelly beans or waste from hives for fuels.

Poctep Symbiosis L: integral use of livestock waste of a farm to produce energy – electricity and heat – through anaerobic digestion.

Salamanca Businesses

Motivation: new lines of work, promote public/private lines of research, financial support.

Problems: Difficulty in obtaining appliances to prepare for reuse, New lines of research (clothes, mattresses,).

Solutions: Provide appliances, materials to prepare them for reuse and / or recycling of parts. Effective financial support.

Remaining Challenges: Promote circular economy (subsidy, incentive).

Compliance with current legislation traceability of materials.

Good Practices: Circular Labs: integrate the Circular Economy into new business models, enabling spaces for creativity, generation of ideas and adaptation to change, accelerating the transition from the « linear » model to the « circular » model based on efficiency in the use of resources.

8. Brainstorming EC2U

In all Think Tanks the participants brainstormed ways of how the EC2U Alliance can become a more circular and sustainable endeavor. **How can we learn from and support each other? How can we enable change? What could the role of EC2U be?**

All collected ideas were assigned to the Knowledge Square (education, research, innovation, service-to-society), a central model and aspiration in the work of EC2U.

Figure 13: The 4 Dimensions of the Knowledge Square

Ideas for the area of research

- Increase research knowledge transfer with the Alliance
- agree on common definition of **circular economy**
- **joint research project** on circular economy and sustainability (application for European funds)
- **collect data** regarding circular initiatives, develop standardized EU measures regarding circularity, implement circular and local EU value chains

Ideas for the area of education

- **Joint workshops /courses/lectures/ modules on circular economy, recognized in joint masters, in EC2U Career Certificate in the diploma supplement or with ECTS**
- **capacity building and training actions with a view to professional opportunities in green jobs**
- **share research resources** across universities

Ideas for the area of innovation

- **“Junior student companies”** can play an important role in the development of projects
- **Living Labs for students**, in collaboration with EC2U partners
- **Digital platform** with easy to find and check indicators (local and EC2U level)

Ideas for the area “service-to-society”

- **University + City:** “A hand-in-hand-approach”
- encouraging cooperation between **institutions and companies**
- develop local networks (**nodes**) to make “pressure” to implement a common framework legislation to treat and process waste
- develop a **reward system** addressed to virtuous stakeholders and nudging policies for virtuous consumers
- **Contest-type events** to encourage recycling for humanitarian causes (event at EC2U level)
- “**Lets' do it**” campaigns for citizens (common for all EC2U partners)
- Involvement of mass media for increased advocacy in all cities from EC2U
- **Newsletters** with best practices from partners, for awareness and nudge to act

Ideas for EC2U events

- **Events:**
 - Plan and organize climate-neutral events within the framework of EC2U
 - No (non-recycled/able) plastic give-aways
 - Considering travel by train if feasible

C. Think Tank Presentation at the 4th EC2U Forum

On April 7, 2022 the Board of WP7 presented the findings of all local Think Tanks including the Brainstorming results and a joint reflection during the 4th EC2U Forum in Pavia. The session took place from 11:30 – 13:00 CET in the Polo Tecnologico. Close to 60 participants followed the presentation on-site. Some participants of the local Think Tanks were also present. The session was recorded and is now [accessible on the EC2U YouTube channel](#).

(See Annex 4 for session slides.)

Figure 14: Inviting people to join the Think Tank Session in Pavia

Figure 16: Impressions of the Think Tank Session at the EC2U Forum in Pavia 07/04/2022 with the WP7 Board Members presenting the local Think Tank results (from middle left to bottom right): James Robert (UPoitiers), Beatrice Re (UPavia), Flora Dausque (UPoitiers), Dana Strauß (UJena), Felipe Roche (UCOimbra), Efrem Yildiz (USalamanca), Adriana Zait, Uiasi).

Audience Engagement

During the Session in Pavia the audience was also encouraged to share their views on two questions:

- Question 1: In your opinion, what is the biggest challenge on the way to circularity?

In the eyes of the audience (N=60) a lack of information/education about the benefits of circularity is the main challenge on the way to a more sustainable society. Followed by the lack of communication between essential stakeholders to promote more systemic thinking and collaboration.

- Question 2: What would you be willing to change to become more “circular”?

- Start workshop in all different school levels and help students get involved in green events using coupons, discounts for public services as trains and buses etc.
- Learn how to grow some food
- don't drink coffee
- Second Hand
- Buy less meat, use a bike, buy only what is necessary, do not buy fast fashion, avoid processed food or food with a huge amount of plastic packaging
- Talk to friends and share ideas
- Reuse coffee waste to enrich plant soil
- Use apps for sharing and second-hand items
- Keep it in mind in every action of the day
- Buy second hand clothes

- Share good habits with friends
 - Use Public transport
 - Use bike or electric motorbike
 - Eat local and without meat
 - First ask if I can borrow Instead of buy
 - less car
 - Less packaging's and plastic
 - Buy second-hand clothes
 - Consume mostly locally
 - Use bicycle more
 - I will not buy if I not really sure ti use
 - Buy less
 - Try to use more sustainable methods for ourselves
 - Be creative
 - Learn to ride a bike
 - Vegan and local food
 - no plastic
 - DIY
 - Taxes on the frontier
 - Go train !
- push green policies on all levels of legislation
 - Went by train as well
 - Be vegetarian
 - Reduce water consuming
 - Add new users, find new uses
 - reduce
 - Do it yourself
 - Equal access to goods
 - Deposit on bottles
 - Don't buy something I'm not going to use
 - Circular communities
 - Sharing
 - pay more for repairable products
 - Reuse, recirculate, don't waste
 - Zero waste
 - give things away to others who can (re)use them
 - More social engaged
 - Educate to recycle
 - Create value to each participant in the game

The results of the live polls were included in the reflections of the Think Tank results and the policy recommendations.

D. Policy Recommendation

The EC2U Think Tank entitled “Circular Economy – Key to Sustainability and Change” took place in spring 2022 in all **seven EC2U locations**. The Think Tank engaged a wide spectrum of stakeholders from across the EC2U Alliance – students, researchers, sustainable development offices at university or city level, business owners, representatives of associations dedicated to the topic.

Each and every one of the stakeholders, **90 in total**, brought fruitful experiences and ideas to the table. This constellation embodied, in an inspiring way, the very core of the EC2U Alliance as a network centered around **research, teaching, innovation, and service to society**.

The Think Tank enables local networking as not all local stakeholders in the field of circular economy knew each other before the event. Thus, the local Think Tanks proved useful as a first step in establishing and **enhancing local networks** that then can act as **strong partners on a European level**. During the **Pavia Forum in April 2022**, this European level was visible at the joint session in which all results were presented.

This policy recommendation identifies fields of action for the future efforts in cultivating a circular economy as the key to sustainability and change with the EC2U Alliance. Sustainability requires continuous collaboration and engagement on all levels. It is the belief of the authors, the Work Package 7 Board Members, that the **EC2U Alliance** with its strategic profile and the instruments it is developing can contribute to the global fight to contain climate change.

The recommendations suggest how to use the results and insights of the Think Tank for the future direction of EC2U and move **from thinking to doing**:

- **In General**: We, the EC2U Partners, recommend fostering engagement and collaboration at different levels both horizontally (chains of organizations, materials, agents etc.) and vertically (between individuals – organizations – city) to tackle the HOW of this complex challenge of circularity in the local as well as in the EC2U context.
- **Vision & Mission**: The EC2U Alliance is a network of researchers, innovators, and change-makers. We recommend continuously strengthening the topic of sustainability in the **vision and mission of EC2U**. It is one vital component of a purposeful

consolidation of a *European Campus of City-Universities* and could serve as a backbone foundation for all EC2U activities.

- **Thematic Extension:** For the second funding phase it will be examined which research areas and United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs) will shape the future directions of EC2U. The authors of this text support the **UNSDGs 12 “Responsible Consumption and Production”** or 13 **“Climate Action”** to direct further research, teaching, innovation and service to society towards circularity. The European Union has yet to develop standardized measures regarding circularity and to implement circular and local EU value chains (<https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/env/items/624232/default>). EC2U research could provide **scientific input** for the decision-making process, collect ideas for the development of a reward system or nudging policies for relevant stakeholders (see e.g. <https://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1065958/FULLTEXT01.pdf>).
- **Network Extension:** As **associations** play a vital part in fostering circularity, we recommend that the EC2U Alliance extend its network and invite relevant associations to become **Associated Partners** of the Alliance. The main objective is to identify synergies among European stakeholders in order to implement and develop circular projects on a long-term scale. A starting point is the **systematic data collection of circular initiatives**. In a further step, EC2U could (help to) develop local networks (nodes) to discuss a common framework legislation to decrease the amount of waste, first, and then to treat and process waste.
- **Standing Topic & Knowledge Exchange:** Sustainability is a core topic of EC2U's Virtual Institute “Sustainable Cities and Communities” (Work Package 6). We recommend including the topic of sustainability also in other EC2U meetings and thus, broaden the range of stakeholders and activities. In terms of content we suggest that the meeting of the **municipalities** and the **students** select sustainability of university cities as a **standing item on the agenda**. The Think Tank has shown that all EC2U universities and cities are underway to more sustainability. The potential for **knowledge exchange** is very high.

- **Circular EC2U:** Building on our joint EC2U mission and the findings of the Think Tank, we recommend that capability of the EC2U Alliance to act as a **change agent** is used to its full extent. As such we, the EC2U Partners, could consider signing a **joint declaration** announcing the **implementation of at least one circular practice** at micro (university), meso (EC2U Alliance) and macro (Partner cities) level.
- **Circular Events:** We recommend that EC2U meetings strive for **carbon-neutrality**. The use of (non-recycled/non-recyclable) plastic merchandise and tableware has to be discouraged and/or at least limited. When traveling eco-friendly options should be taken into consideration. These commitments could be part of the joint declaration.
- **Incorporation into EC2U Research & Education Instruments/Offers:** We, the EC2U Partners, recommend looking for opportunities within the EC2U **research and teaching activities** to implement the topic of circular economy and sustainability, e.g. a PhD thesis or school projects in the framework of the **Virtual Institute** on “Sustainable Cities and Communities”. We further recommend to encourage students to engage in designated extra-curricular activities to be recognized by the **Career Plan Certificate**. The EC2U App “**My Mobile Tutor**” could list and link such offers. Alternatively, the EC2U Engagement Stage or a community platform like Climate Hub could be used by the EC2U Partners to make existing local offers visible and encourage the students to engage locally but also while they are staying abroad at one of the EC2U Partner universities. Furthermore, we recommend that the offers of the **Entrepreneurial Academy** and **Entrepreneurial Academy Week** address circular and sustainable entrepreneurship.
- **Open Communication:** **Sensemaking and awareness** have to be accelerated on a local as well as on the European level. The poll during the EC2U Forum in Pavia showed that the **lack of information and education** is regarded as the main challenge on the way to a more sustainable society. *What is circular economy? What does it mean to us and in relation to us? What does it prompt us to think and do?* We recommend that the EC2U Partners continue the **open dialogue** that kicked off with the Think Tank. Universities, municipalities, and sustainable businesses have done pioneering work in the field. We recommend that all stakeholders communicate their efforts and encourage **public discourse** on the topic. EC2U-, University- or city-wide events, e.g. more

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prominent position of the topic on websites, more social media posts on the topic,
Sustainability Days/Weeks, joint workshops, info material for schools.

III. Annexes

A. Annex 1 – Think Tank Charter

THINK TANK CHARTER

Charter for participants and event organizers* involved in the EC2U THINK TANK

One of the goals of the EC2U Alliance is to foster the dialogue within our communities and within Europe, to reach out and bring different stakeholders together to discuss the central issues of our time. The EC2U Think Tank is a safe place of respectful exchange and constructive discussion. All participants and organizers acknowledge and support this bedrock of the Think Tank for the best of everyone involved.

EC2U is the abbreviation for European Campus of City-Universities. EC2U is a multi-cultural and multi-lingual Alliance consisting of seven long-standing, education- and research-led, locally and globally engaged universities from four diverse regions of the European Union: the University of Coimbra, the University of Iasi, the University of Jena, the University of Pavia, the University of Poitiers (Coordinator), the University of Salamanca and the University of Turku.

As a participant in the THINK TANK, I commit to:

- Contribute to the debate on the priorities for our common future, together with stakeholders from all backgrounds within our local community and within the EC2U Alliance.
- Respect our European values, as set in Art. 2 of the Treaty on the European Union: human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities, which is part of what it means to be European and to engage respectfully with each other. These values are common to all EU Member States and implicitly EC2U members in a society in which pluralism, non-discrimination, tolerance, justice, solidarity and equality between women and men must prevail.
- Contribute to the THINK TANK with constructive and concrete proposals, respecting the opinions of other speakers and building Europe's future together, starting with my city and the EC2U community.
- Refrain from expressing, disseminating, or sharing content which is illegal, hateful or deliberately false or misleading. In this context, I will always refer to credible and reliable sources when I share content and information to support my ideas.

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- Participate in the THINK TANK based on my own free will, and I will not try to use the THINK TANK to pursue any commercial or exclusively private interests.

As a party organizing a THINK TANK, I commit to:

- Allow everyone to express their voice freely and equally consider all expressed views.
- Promote events that are inclusive and accessible for all citizens, including by publishing the details of the event in English and the local language on a digital platform.
- Encourage diversity in the debates, by actively supporting the participation of citizens from all walks of life, irrespective of gender, sexual orientation, age, socioeconomic background, religion and/or level of education.
- Respect freedom of speech, giving space to competing opinions and proposals – as long as they are neither hateful nor illegal.
- Whenever possible and relevant, favor the cross-board participation of citizens in the events.
- Guarantee full transparency. Following the event, I will report openly on the outcome of the Think Tank to the WP 7 Board. The WP 7 Board uses the reports for a presentation at the EC2U Forum and a joint policy recommendation.
- When providing participants with information on topics for debate (e.g. digital, print or audio-visual material), ensure that is accurate, reliable, accessible and has traceable references.
- Ensure compliance with EU data protection and privacy rules.
- Use only the agreed upon visual identity for communicating the event.

Citizens and partner organizations wishing to take active part in the THINK TANK shall abide by this Charter.

**The Think Tank Charta is partly taken from the Charta of the Conference on the Future of Europe in the spirit of which the Think Tank is taking place.*

EC2U is the abbreviation for European Campus of City-Universities. EC2U is a multi-cultural and multi-lingual Alliance consisting of seven long-standing, education- and research-led, locally and globally engaged universities from four diverse regions of the European Union: the University of Coimbra, the University of Iasi, the University of Jena, the University of Pavia, the University of Poitiers (Coordinator), the University of Salamanca and the University of Turku.

B. Annex 2 – List of Participants

Turku

- Riikka Leskinen, Head of Department, Valonia / Regional Council of Southwest Finland
- Outi Laikko, Senior Advisor, City of Turku
- Linda Fröberg-Niemi, Director, Clean Turku, Turku Business Region
- Jutta Mäkinen, Development Specialist in Sustainable Development, University of Turku
- Anu Bask, University Lecturer, University of Turku
- Leena Setälä, Director of Sustainable Development, Intermunicipal Hospital District of Southwest Finland
- Veera Pajunen, Member of the Board, The Student Union of the University of Turku
- Miia Jylhä, Research and Development Supervisor, Lounais-Suomen Jätehuolto [Southwest Finland Waste Management]
- Jari-Pekka Tulonen, Health Inspector, City of Turku
- Hannu Visuri, Member of the Board, Association for Consumers in Southwest Finland
- Satu Teerikangas, Professor, University of Turku

Poitiers

- Laurent Brizzi, Vice-President Campus Life and Heritage, University of Poitiers
- Marie Ferru, Professor of Geography, University of Poitiers
- Sandra Lardier, Head of the Circular Economy Unit, Grand Poitiers Urban Community
- Florent Boissou, Co-founder, BioseDev
- Julien Souquet Grumey, Co-founder, BioseDev
- Emilie Guichard, PhD student at the University of Poitiers, Psychology of pro-environmental behaviours, Biowaste source separation behaviours, Social acceptability.
- Mathis Navard, PhD student at the University of Poitiers, "Ecological transition and information-communication: optimising awareness campaigns on waste management".
- Anais Canteau, Co-founder, association la FaBrick
- Marine Lavaud, Co-founder, association la FaBrick
- Anne Claire Boisson, Co-founder, association la FaBrick

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Jena

- Sina Leipold – Head of Environmental Politics at the Helmholtz-Center for Environmental Research Leipzig/Professor of Environmental Politics at the University of Jena
- Anya Schwamberger, City of Jena, Department for Urban Development and Environment
- Luisa Wöllner – European Student Network Jena
- Thomas Sauer – em. Professor of Economics at the University of Applied Science Jena (Ernst-Abbe-Hochschule)
- Michaela Jahn-Neubert – Chairperson of „Initiative Inner City“ (association of all business owners in the inner city of Jena)
- Robin Muggenthaler – Head of Green Office at the University of Jena
- Nicoleta Reinhardt, City of Jena, Department for Urban Development and Environment

Pavia

- Davide Barbieri - UNIPV Mobility Manager
- Diego Bosco - General Secretary Generale Italtotec
- Alessandro Maranesi - Dean Ghislieri College
- Davide Griffini - General Secretary Borromeo College
- Andrea Campotaro - OSA Office for Sustainable Actions
- Piero Malcovati - VoltaPlant
- Caterina Bono - Sales LAVGON
- Vittorio Biondi - Assolombarda
- Enrico Doria - Founder Biorestart
- Daniela Buonocore - Founder Biorestart
- Angelo Di Benedetto - Cofounder Planeat
- Laura Gallo - Founder FungoBox and Coffeefrom
- Gianluca Curacchi - S.T.E.P ESN - Erasmus Students Network
- Giulia Marrazzo - Cittadinanza attiva
- Cosimo Lacava - Il Sellino Spiritato
- Marco Fimognari - Founder Re-Cig
- Chiara Riccardi - Fiab Federazione Italiana Ambiente e Bicicletta Pavia

- Greta Caglioti - Banco alimentare
- Michael A. Richards - Repair Café

Coimbra

- Patrícia Pereira da Silva - Pro-Rector University of Coimbra for Planning and Sustainable Development
- Filipe Rocha - Head of Planning, Management and Development Unit and Coordinator of Sustainable Development Office
- Alexandra Aragão and Susana Jorge - Teacher
- Denner Nunes (PhD Student) - Researcher
- Filipe Carvalheiro and Edgar Mendes - University Environment Division
- Francisco Silva (President) and Tomás Ramos - ESN Coimbra
- Daniel Aragão Seco (Vice-President) and Luís Martins - Associação Académica de Coimbra/ Sustainability Police
- Emília Oliveira - Associação Académica de Coimbra- Ecology Nucleous
- Joana Loureiro (representative at EC2U) and António Martins (expert) - Câmara Municipal de Coimbra
- Alexandra Rodrigues (representative at EC2U) and Ana Pires (expert) - Comissão de Coordenação e Desenvolvimento Regional do Centro
- Fátima Matias (representative at EC2U) and Jorge Corker (expert) - Instituto Pedro Nunes
- Solve – João Azevedo - Junior Student Business

Iasi

- Adrian Andrei - Expert at ADRNE (North-East Regional Development Agency)
- Paul Butnariu - President of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry Iasi
- Dan Adrian Chelaru - Group Sustainability Officer, Iulius Group Iasi (mixed use urban regeneration projects, real estate and commercial developer)
- Marius Alexa - Arhipelago (communication, national business conferences, international economic missions, entrepreneurial projects, corporate responsibility)

- Elvys Sandu Prisecaru - President of the Association “Mai bine. Etic. Ecologic. Echitabil” (environmental protection, social economy, socially responsible initiatives)
- Florin Constantin Mihai - Researcher at the UAIC Interdisciplinary Research Institute, specialised in Urban/Rural Sociology Geoinformatics (GIS) Geostatistics Geography Waste Management Environmental Science
- Razvan Ionut Druga - Doctoral student at UAIC, corporate responsibility and corporate image
- Mara Matcu - Doctoral student at UAIC, ethical and moral responsibility in business

Salamanca

- Alfredo de Miguel de Pablos, representative of the Chamber of Commerce of Salamanca
- Juan Carlos Martín Muñoz, head of the Environment Service (regional government)
- Pilar Rodríguez Sánchez, cooperative of social initiative PORSIETE
- Julián Juanes Fraile, vicepresident of the Agrarian Association ASAJA
- Juan Bautista Alonso, manager of Local Action Group ADRISS
- Cristina Leon, head of the Innovation area of ITACYL (regional government)
- Sara Olmedo, head of Livestock Research area of ITACYL (regional government)
- Carlos Arnes Fiz, head of Waste and Contaminated Soil Service of the General Direction of Quality and Environmental Sustainability (regional government)
- Javier Carbonero and Mar Marcos, Green Office of the Usal

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C. Annex 3 – Think Tank Script

2nd EC2U Think Tank SCRIPT “Circular Economy – Key to Change and Sustainability”

Content & Outcome Plan for local Think Tank meetings

[Internal use for WP 7 Board Members]

1. In a nutshell

Motivation	As a catalyst for ideas the Think Tanks enable the circulation of knowledge and solutions. They are designed to open an exchange between citizens, scientists and policy makers to discuss pressing societal issues. The EC2U Think Tanks are a way of learning from each other on a local and European level. They help to come up with ways of getting involved, of participating and enabling change faster.
Outcome	Formulate local problems and solutions in building up a circular economy. The output (text) will serve as the groundwork for an EC2U-wide panel at the Forum in Pavia (5-7 April 2022) and a policy recommendation to be published on EC2U channels by 30 April 2022.
Topic	Circular Economy - Key to Change and Sustainability
Timing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Local events: January/(early) February 2022 B. Forum session: 5-7 April 2022 C. Policy Recommendation (target group: EC2U universities and cities): deadline 30 April 2022
Format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A. Closed session at each location. 5-10 people around a conference table, moderated by WP7 Board Member. B. Open session at EC2U Forum in Pavia. Board Members present results. EC2U partners and interested public is invited to join. C. Written document for online dissemination.
Participants	Representatives of EC2U Stakeholder groups, e.g. students, researchers, green offices, stakeholders from industry & city municipalities, citizens, teachers etc.

2. Proposed Procedure

Before the event

- invite participants
 - e.g. **You are invited to share your on-the-ground, real-life experience from your area of work/expertise/engagement that aim to implement circular economy or circular principles.** Tell us about your motivation to become active, the challenges you tackled, the solutions you came up with and the remaining problems that you face. In addition, we'd love to hear your ideas on how to make such an entity as a European Alliance of city-universities more sustainable. **Let's brainstorm together!**
 - The Think Tank brings stakeholders from different backgrounds together. **It aims to create a culture of open dialogue** where we learn from each other on a local and European level. Together we want to discuss the pressing challenges of our time and enable change.
 - The Think Tank will take place in all seven EC2U cities. In April 2022, the results of the seven Think Tanks will be presented at the public EC2U Forum in Pavia. A joint policy recommendation, written by the hosts of the Think Tanks, will be based on the outcomes of the local Think Tanks.

- explain what EC2U is
 - e.g. **The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U) is a** multi-cultural Alliance consisting of seven universities: the University of Coimbra (Portugal), Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi (Romania), the University of Jena (Germany), the University of Pavia (Italy), the University of Poitiers (France-Coordinator), the University of Salamanca (Spain) and the University of Turku (Finland). **Working together in the fields of education and research, the Alliance also aims to create societal impact by engaging in the fields of innovation and service to society.**
 - EC2U will **develop an innovative space allowing mobility to flow freely between the seven universities and associated cities, by creating a pan-European campus,** connected by the common European identity, contributing to the creation of a smart higher education eco-system through a new model of quality education for an inclusive civic society. This unique model relies on a double **vertical and horizontal integration strategy**, producing synergies from education, research and innovation, from formal/non-formal/informal education, and from the involvement of academic communities, municipalities, higher education regulatory bodies, socio-economic entities, citizens.

- give short summary of what we mean by circular economy and its relation to sustainability
 - e.g. **The topic of the Think Tank is “Circular economy – Key to Change and Sustainability”.** Circular economy consists of three principles: 1. Eliminate waste and pollution, 2. Circulate products and materials (keep products and material in use as much as possible), 3. Regenerate nature. “We must transform every element of our take-make-waste system: how we manage resources, how we make and use products, and what we do with the materials afterwards. Only then can we create a thriving circular economy that can benefit everyone within the limits of our planet. [...] **The circular economy gives us the tools to tackle climate change and biodiversity loss together, while addressing important social needs**” (ellenmacarthurfoundation.org). Circular economy is not an end in itself but a means to an end: better environmental quality, economic growth and social well-being.
 - Circular economy and Sustainability have many things in common, as well as controversial or debatable issues. We are interested in the ways in which circular economy can increase sustainability. **Sustainability** refers to a development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987). “**Sustainability can be defined as a situation in which human activity is conducted to conserve the functions of the earth’s ecosystems, or a transformation of human lifestyle that increases the likelihood that living conditions will continuously support security, well-being, and health, particularly by maintaining the supply of non-replaceable goods and services, or an indefinite perpetuation of all life forms**”. (Geissdoerfer et al, 2017)

- introduce Think Tank Charter
 - see extra document

At the event

- Welcome by WP 7 Board Member
- Introduction of the topic by an expert
- Presentation and discussions of examples by stakeholders
 - Outcome see below

3. Outcome

Written documentation of the following two tasks:

1. Collect sets of examples promoting circular economy and/or sustainable actions in your university, in your city, in your companies. In particular, ask each stakeholder:

- Question 1: What motivated/motivates the stakeholders to become engaged in circular economy?
 - Collect the motivations of the stakeholders.
 - Identify the main areas in which the stakeholder has experiences and/or areas considered as being very important at local level (e.g. companies can have specific areas – like waste, for a local garbage collecting company, or pollution etc, while NGOs, administration and policy people may have several areas of interest)
- Question 2: What are the specific problems and challenges that the stakeholders have attempted to solve?
 - Collect the initial problems and challenges.
- Question 3: Which solutions did the stakeholders come up with and implement? What helped them along the way? What hindered them along the way?
 - Collect solutions.
- Question 4: What are the next challenges that the stakeholders want to tackle/Or: What are problems that they yet have to solve?
 - Collect unsolved problems

2. Brainstorm ways in which the EC2U Alliance can become a more sustainable endeavor.

- Question 5: What ideas do the stakeholders have to make the alliance more circular:

1. in general: How can we learn from and support each other? How can we enable change? What could the role of EC2U be?
2. in our joint EC2U endeavors: joint events, mobilities, merchandising etc.
 - Offering creative and feasible ideas.

➔ In the end, the written documentation of each Think Tank will be summarized in this table:

UPavia	Motivations WHY	Area/Topic	Challenges	Solutions	Remaining problems	Ideas for EC2U
Stakeholder university						
Stakeholder city						
Stakeholder company						
UPoitiers	Motivations WHY		Challenges	Solutions	Remaining problems	Ideas for EC2U
Stakeholder university						
Stakeholder city						
Stakeholder company						
UIasi	Motivations WHY		Challenges	Solutions	Remaining problems	Ideas for EC2U
Stakeholder university						
Stakeholder city						
Stakeholder company						
UTurku	Motivations WHY		Challenges	Solutions	Remaining problems	Ideas for EC2U
Stakeholder university						
Stakeholder city						
Stakeholder company						

UCoimbra	Motivations WHY		Challenges	Solutions	Remaining problems	Ideas for EC2U
Stakeholder university						
Stakeholder city						
Stakeholder company						
USalamanca	Motivations WHY		Challenges	Solutions	Remaining problems	Ideas for EC2U
Stakeholder university						
Stakeholder city						
Stakeholder company						
UJena	Motivations WHY		Challenges	Solutions	Remaining problems	Ideas for EC2U
Stakeholder university						
Stakeholder city						
Stakeholder company						

4. Public Session @ EC2U Forum in Pavia

The synthesized outcomes of the local Think Tanks will

- stimulate public debate and
- identify good ideas that can be acted upon.

We will use the contents of the above table to show:

- What motivates the stakeholders to become active? What drives them?
 - Show common values
 - Show links to UNSDGs (and maybe already collect arguments in which UNSDGs the alliance should engage next)
 - Learn about motifs from other partners to encourage own stakeholders
- In which areas are the stakeholders active?
 - Show the diversity of areas to engage in
 - Inspire stakeholders to become engaged in new fields
 - Find people from the EC2U community who are engaged in the same field for exchange
 - Encourage experience and knowledge exchange

- Which problems did they encounter?
- Which the solutions did they find?
 - The struggle is real
 - Identify conditions of success
 - Enable partners with similar problems to identify (other) solutions of the EC2U partners
 - Encourage experience and knowledge exchange
- Ideas for the EC2U community
 - Evaluation of the potential for the alliance to become more circular and sustainable
 - Find new partners and new networks

➔ Invite all stakeholders from the Think Tanks to the Forum (an audience member)

5. Policy Recommendation

The written policy recommendation will be published online on all EC2U channels and provide a reference point for future events and actions.

EC2U WP7 Board will write the policy recommendation.

1. **Introduction:** Very brief passage on the findings of the first Think Tank (Survey #Value4YourVaues – April 2021) and the motivation behind the second Think Tank (show value set)
2. **Showcases:** Best practices examples with identified conditions of success
3. **From the Think Tank to the Do Tank:** List concrete ways to make EC2U more sustainable, e.g. the EC2U Forum, the mobilities, the website etc.; also think about ways to incorporate the topics of “circular economy” and “sustainability” permanently into the core of EC2U

European Campus
of City-Universities

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D. Annex 4 – Session slides

Co-funded by the
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2nd EC2U Think Tank

Circular Economy Key to Sustainability and Change

2022

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Agenda

1. Think Tank Concept + Think Tank Charta
2. Think Tank *Circular Economy* –
Key to Sustainability and Change
3. Ideas for our EC2U Alliance
4. Joint Reflection

EC2U THINK TANK

The Think Tank aims to create a culture of **open dialogue** where we learn from each other on a **local and European level**. Together we want to discuss the challenges of our time and enable **change**.

EC2U THINK TANK CHARTA

“As a participant in the THINK TANK, I commit to:

*Respecting our European values, as set in Art. 2 of the Treaty on the European Union: **human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, including the rights of persons belonging to minorities, which is part of what it means to be European and to engage respectfully with each other.**”*

1st THINK TANK (2021)

Value4yourValues

- The 1st Think Tank was developed on the subject of **values** – the **core of all human actions**, including education, research, networking, engagement and collaboration in society.
- Online **survey** translated into **nine languages**; 6th-30th April 202, **1.400** participants

CHANGE

What has to **change** in our society so that you can live according to your values ?

2nd THINK TANK (2022)

**Circular economy – Key to
Change and Sustainability**

Question to you: What does „circular“ mean to you?

<https://app.sli.do/event/6BFGkUVEPWqFJfoh8f8vnm>

2nd THINK TANK (2022)

Circular economy – Key to Change and Sustainability

- Circular economy consists of three **principles**: 1. Eliminate waste and pollution, 2. Circulate products and materials, 3. Regenerate nature.
- We understand **circular economy** not as an end in itself but as a **means to an end**: better environmental quality, economic growth and social well-being.

2nd Think Tank PARTICIPANTS

7 local sessions, 90 participants

Thanks to all Think Tank participants!

2nd Think Tank QUESTIONS

MOTIVATION

Question 1: What is the motivation of the stakeholders to engage in circular economy?

PROBLEMS

Question 2: What are the specific problems that the stakeholders have attempted to solve?

SOLUTIONS

Question 3: Which solutions did the stakeholders come up with?

REMAINING CHALLENGES

Question 4: What are problems that have yet have to be solved?

FINDINGS

National Background

- **Different national approaches in how to implement circular economy**

National Background

	Municipal waste (p.a. per person)	Food waste (p.a. per person)	Municipal recycling rate	Share of goods traded that are recyclable raw materials	Material reuse rate	Patents related to circular economy (since 2000)	Investment in circular economy sectors
FINLAND	504 kg	189 kg	42%	0.06%	7%	111	€2M
FRANCE	511 kg	136 kg	42%	0.24%	18%	542	€21.3M
GERMANY	627 kg	149 kg	66%	0.25%	11%	1260	€28.7M
ITALY	497 kg	179 kg	45%	0.19%	19%	294	€17.8M
PORTUGAL	461 kg	132 kg	31%	0.26%	2%	22	€1.4M
ROMANIA	261 kg	76 kg	13%	0.13%	2%	34	€1.1M
SPAIN	443 kg	135 kg	30%	0.20%	8%	210	€11.0M

RESULTS *TURKU*

Motivation

Problems

Solutions

Remaining Challenges

University

To proactively foster **well-being and a sustainable future** through University's missions (education, research, third mission) and everyday activities

Requires **communicating and implementing new ways of thinking** and doing which take time.

Sustainable Campus Action Plan in the making to promote to the university community **everyday actions** following the principles of sustainability

Raising awareness

City

Strive towards **sustainable city development** to create positive impacts on well-being, economy (new businesses) and environment

Costs and rush stall decision-making. Multi-stakeholder collaboration requires better understanding of different actors' role and smart decision-making

Make **investment and procurement decisions** aligned with CE; **process and share information for different stakeholders.**

Take steps **from plans to concrete implementation.**
Focus next on **transportation and mobility**

Business

To be an influencer in the industrial policy and support circular economy in different parts of the value chain

Lack of investment funds.
Broad systemic thinking is needed instead of optimizing only selected parts of the system.

Measuring footprints and creating ecosystems (actors, knowledge, research) **around different material streams.**

Issuing **stronger enforcement measures** e.g. via VAT exemption and obligation to recycle and **instructions to procuring units** from suppliers.

GOOD PRACTICES *TURKU*

UNIVERSITY

Sustainable Campus Life Working Group
Carbon neutrality by 2025

Photos: Hanna Oksanen

CITY

Circular Turku Roadmap

BUSINESS

Circular Economy Visitor Centre brings circular economy to life, by, first, functioning as a learning environment for citizens and school children, second, being a showroom for regional companies and other operators in the region; and third, acting as a builder of cooperation networks.

RESULTS *POITIERS*

Motivation

Problems

Solutions

Remaining Challenges

University

Steering the process and meeting students' expectations

Environmental actions are sometimes **in contradiction with general public contracting rules**

Introduce sustainability and social responsibility criteria in contracts

Generalise sustainable development and social responsibility criteria in **procurement.**

City

Work with all the actors of the territory on the themes of short cycles and recovery

Supporting change in habits and behaviour

Conducting a **psychological study** with the help of a PhD student

Pursue and implement actions to promote behavioural change

Business

Being a committed, **ecologically-minded entrepreneur**

Work with French products that have real **traceability** and respect the types of protocols already in place

Working with natural + minimally processed materials using a process that respects the environment + the charter of labels

Moving from laboratory experimentation as part of a start-up to **production on an industrial scale**

GOOD PRACTICES POITIERS

UNIVERSITY

Obtained the DDRS label to implement its commitment to the ecological and energy transition

<https://www.label-ddrs.org/>

BUSINESS

A process for deconstructing biosourced and renewable plant material (dry with metal balls and therefore without solvents or water) to extract molecules with specific properties.

<https://biosedev.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/4.jpg>

CITY

Setting up collective composting sites

© Photo NR

RESULTS JENA

Motivation

Problems

Solutions

Remaining Challenges

University

Work together and get others involved for change
Research: define the concept

Technological solutions easier than **systemic solutions**

Implement an **institutional structure** and attribute a **fixed budget** for sustainability issues.

High consumption of heat and energy in university facilities.
Address social sustainability

City

Create of a **livable** and **environmentally friendly city**

Communicate and implement change within the current political and legal frameworks.
Personnel and financial shortage

Strategically implement **circular concepts** in city policy, in city events or daycare centers. Enabling circulation among citizens.

Adapt existing buildings and their surroundings to **climate change**.
Develop infrastructure for sustainable mobility

Business

Create a **better world** for future generations. Implement new sustainability regulations

Sensitize entrepreneurs to Circular Economy
Staff and financial shortage

Implement sustainable guidelines for **procurement**

Raise awareness and **prevent waste** in the first place

GOOD PRACTICES JENA

UNIVERSITY

Green Office
Sustainability Working Group with
the Senate
Pallet furniture for the Campus

Foto: Robin Muggenthaler,
Green Office UJena

CITY

Repair cafés
Food-sharing projects
Give away shelves
Fairy tale booklet for
schools
Fair shopping guide

<https://zebraluchs.de/moehrchenheft>

Business

Refill Jena
Promotion of regional
products

Foto: Thomas Stridde, OTZ Jena

RESULTS PAVIA

Motivation

Problems

Solutions

Remaining Challenges

University

Reduce the use of private vehicles and related CO2 emissions. **Reduce waste** and increase students' awareness about environmental issues

Getting the civil society and local stakeholders involved, lack of local actors' proactive behaviors

Increase the **communication** and the engagement activities

Coordination and cooperation with other local stakeholders

City

Reduce urban waste (food, appliances, cigarettes). Spread the idea of sustainable mobility

Enhance the **collaboration with public and private actors** and promote a non-consumerist logic based on re-conceptualizing the idea of waste

Spread the **culture of sustainability**, create synergies among actors, engage citizens through **workshops/city tours**

More commitment is needed from public authorities, legislative frameworks need to **be updated** with respect to circular practices (e.g. concept of waste)

Business

Transform "waste" into resources, develop alternative, ethical and socially responsible ways of producing

Create industrial symbiosis, communicate the value proposition to prospect clients, scaling-up

Find partnering firms, diversify the product portfolio, **innovate**

Scaling up, communicate the value proposition, encourage producers to shift to the circular economy paradigm

GOOD PRACTICES PAVIA

BUSINESS

- Transform what is commonly defined as « waste » into a resource
- Reduce the food waste
- Propose sustainable alternatives to fast fashion

UNIVERSITY

- Establishment of OSA - Office for Sustainable Actions
- Bike sharing to move in town
- Installation of water dispensers in several university sites
- Increase students' awareness (colleges)

CITY

- Repair Café
- FIAB: promoting sustainable mobility
- Spreading among citizens the circular practices (e.g., events Plasticfree)

RESULTS COIMBRA

Motivation

Problems

Solutions

Remaining Challenges

University

contribute to a **sustainable future** and to the adoption of life models that consider and respect the human dimension, with sustainability practices to be consciously implemented in the management of the entity itself, to be transmitted through **teaching** and to be developed by research (new solutions and new paths to circularity)

the **intense daily activity** of universities generates environmental impacts, with overuse of resources and exorbitant production of waste, resulting from the consumption of resources in UC spaces, the travels made and the behavior of each and every one who works, studies or simply visits it

political commitment and a Strategic Plan with a pillar “environment and climate action”, with a clear vision
+
a dedicated office
+
very active student associations

energy inefficiency of historic buildings; traffic in the historic area; specific **waste streams needing integrated management procedures**; promote the use of goods with reused materials & legal barriers; raise general awareness of an academic community of almost 30,000 people; **improve circularity indicators and own ecological footprint measurement model**

City

awareness of all the community in the practices of circularity; **conservation of resources** based on the natural heritage; reduce the city production of emissions and waste; decelerate/ **minimize the effects of climate change**

indifference generated by inaction and **lack of political prioritization** of cities to CE cultural issues: consumer behavior or the lack of knowledge about the CE concept and its implications

first step: developing a “**Roadmap for the Circular Economy**”

removal of issues of circularity of the economy from the priorities of the political agenda

Business

need to awaken and support business to the urgency of developing and implementing new materials, technologies and business models that allow greater resource efficiency and a more sustainable development of our economy

need to **increase the use of materials** from renewable sources, to reduce of waste production throughout the life cycle of products, to upcycle, to improve energy efficiency, to **increase durability and extension of life time of products** and to apply systems sensing and dematerialization

dematerialization and materials engineering, search for more efficient materials / technologies / solutions, focus on safe and sustainable design, eco-design; life cycle analysis; increasing the sustainability of non-circular solutions

prioritize the use of renewable raw materials from the agroforestry sector and boost the flow of national industrial materials to develop new products, with a focus on energy efficiency, sustainability and circularity; **business still very focused on the costs of transitioning to circular solutions and with difficult access to financing**

GOOD PRACTICES COIMBRA

UNIVERSITY

- Political determination and involvement:
 - **Strategic Plan** with a pillar “Environment and climate action”
 - **Sustainable Development Office**
 - **Sustainable Development Observatory**
 - **Dedicated webpage** (www.uc.pt/en/sustainability)
- **Sustainability Guide** to Students
- **Energy for Sustainability Initiative**
- **Climate clock** (the first climate clock in Portugal was inaugurated at the Academic Association of Coimbra - AAC)
- **Green Community** (implementation of initiatives to make events more sustainable – e.g.: reducing the use of environmentally unfriendly materials)

CITY / REGION

- **Roadmap for the Circular Economy** (in development by Municipality)
- **Centro Green Deal** (circular public purchases with CE principles)
- **Regional Institutional Pact for Circular Economy**

BUSINESS

- **“Hands On”** - workshops to help developing business circular strategies
- Services to **support the development of business models** that are as “circular” as possible
- **leUC - E-Waste** (waste of electrical and electronic equipment)

RESULTS IASI

Motivation

Problems

Solutions

Remaining Challenges

Business
City
University

Similar for all three category of stakeholders - intrinsic (individual and organizational level) and extrinsic: **personal values** (desire to change things for the better), **organizational values** (environmental and social responsibility) and **financial opportunities** (call for projects available)

Lack of trust in own power to move things in the good direction
Lack of circular economy formal **education**

Reduced citizen involvement
Reluctant entrepreneurs

Lack of **traceability + verifiable indicators**, Deficient secondary legislation (for applying rules)
State institutions prefer classic paper

Networking and common projects

Training and technical assistance
Iasi participant in „**Zero Waste Municipalities**“

Personal initiatives and involvement
Clusters of creative industries
Social enterprises

Increase **intersectorial collaboration**
Increase funds for research in the field

Reduce the risk of „**greenwashing**“
Increase waste management infrastructures, mainly in rural areas

Develop the **market for recycled materials**
Increase all stakeholders' awareness

GOOD PRACTICES IASI

The Urban Center for Good Initiatives - CUIB

multidimensional space (bistro, local products store, space for cultural and educational events). Aims to support local producers and community, diminish negative impact on environment.

REDU - Reused, Recycled and Upcycled Clothes and Accessories” (Green Group)

Integrated and total waste management solutions for 6 main waste streams associated with households and SMEs (WEEE, plastics, PET, glass, lighting bulbs, cardboard)

ECOTIC Caravan

educational project aiming to raise awareness on environmental protection and sustainable development, focusing on household, electrical and electronic waste (HEEW). Designed for both general public and children aged 6-14 years.

Mobile exhibition with disassembled HEEW, to increase awareness towards risks of poor electric-waste management.

RESULTS SALAMANCA

Motivation

Contribute to sustainable development, from research, training and knowledge transfer to society

Problems

Structural inertia and bureaucracy
lack of coordination
Very limited budgets

Solutions

Achievable objectives at the university and municipal levels
Facilitate participatory forums and communication channels

Remaining Challenges

Promote multidisciplinary teams
Reduce the **carbon footprint** + energy expenditure in institutions

City/
University
Agriculture/
farming
Business

Take advantage of our natural resources and the especially **organic by-products** of the agri-food sector
solution for rural depopulation

reduce production costs
coordination among administration, industry, scientific community + consumers

invest in R + D + I
encourage symbiosis strategies among industries (waste from one industry can be the raw material of another)
New degrees and masters

new lines of work
promote public/private lines of research
financial support

Difficulty in obtaining appliances to prepare for reuse
New lines of research (clothes, mattresses,)

Provide appliances, materials to prepare them **for reuse** and / or recycling of parts.
effective financial support

Promote circular economy (subsidy, incentive)
Compliance with current legislation
traceability of materials

GOOD PRACTICES SALAMANCA

Circular Labs

integrate the Circular Economy into new business models, enabling spaces for creativity, generation of ideas and adaptation to change, accelerating the transition from the « linear » model to the « circular » model based on efficiency in the use of resources.

Poctep Reinova_S.i.

pilot experiences with companies that used their kale waste to make other products such as cookies or snacks, waste from making jams to make jelly beans or waste from hives for fuels.

Poctep Symbiosis L

integral use of livestock waste of a farm to produce energy – electricity and heat – through anaerobic digestion

Question to you: In your opinion, what is the biggest challenge on the way to circularity?

1. **Lack of communication** – *How to enhance the communication between essential stakeholders to promote systemic thinking and collaboration?*
2. **Lack of information/ education** – *How to inform/educate people with different educational levels, backgrounds and cultures about the benefits of circularity?*
3. **Lack of understanding (What is waste?)** – *How to support data-driven decision-making by transforming the monitoring and analysis of (understanding) of “waste”?*
4. **Lack of financial resources** – *How to start a reward/support systems to promote circularity and sustainability among organizations as well as individuals?*
5. **Lack of agency** – *How to engage in circular economy (and gain momentum)?*

<https://app.sli.do/event/6BFGkUVEPWqFJfoh8f8vnm>

Ideas for our EC2U Alliance

BRAINSTORMING EC2U

KNOWLEDGE ECOSYSTEM

BRAINSTORMING EC2U

- Increase research knowledge transfer with the Alliance
- agree on common definition of **circular economy**
- **joint research project** on circular economy and sustainability (application for European funds)
- **collect data** regarding circular initiatives, develop standardized EU measures regarding circularity, implement circular and local EU value chains

BRAINSTORMING EC2U

- **Joint** workshops /courses/lectures/modules on circular economy, recognized in joint masters, in EC2U Career Certificate in the diploma supplement or with ECTS
- **capacity building** and **training actions** with a view to professional opportunities in green jobs
- **share research resources** across universities

BRAINSTORMING EC2U

- **“Junior student companies”** can play an important role in the development of projects
- **Living Labs for students**, in collaboration with EC2U partners
- **Digital platform** with easy to find and check indicators (local and EC2U level)

BRAINSTORMING EC2U

- **University + City:** “A hand-in-hand-approach”
- encouraging cooperation between **institutions and companies**
- develop local networks (**nodes**) to make “pressure” to implement a common framework legislation to treat and process waste
- develop a **reward system** addressed to virtuous stakeholders and nudging policies for virtuous consumers
- **Contest**-type events to encourage recycling for humanitarian causes (event at EC2U level)
- **“Lets’ do it“** campaigns for citizens (common for all EC2U partners)
- Involvement of mass media for increased advocacy in all cities from EC2U
- **Newsletters** with best practices from partners, for awareness and nudge to act

BRAINSTORMING EC2U

- **Events:**
 - Plan and organize climate-neutral events within the framework of EC2U
 - No (non-recycled/able) plastic give-aways
 - Considering travel by train if feasible

Question to you: What would you be willing to change to become more „circular“?

<https://app.sli.do/event/6BFGkUVEPWqFJfoh8f8vnm>

REFLECTION

- We should accelerate **sensemaking and awareness** – What is this? What does it mean to us and in relation to us? What does it prompt us to think and do?
- We should foster **engagement and collaboration** in different levels both **horizontally** (chains of organizations, materials, agents etc.) and **vertically** (between individuals – organizations – city) to tackle the **HOW** of this complex challenge in the **local as well as in the EC2U context**.
- **Associations** play a vital part in this topic. We should reach out to and collaborate with associations dedicated to the topic.
- We should look for opportunities within the **EC2U research and teaching** activities to implement the topic of circular economy (e.g. Virtual Institutes, Career Certificate, Entrepreneurial Academy)

Let's do it.

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Please note that the content of this activity / deliverable is available in the different languages of the EC2U Alliance upon request.